

Get up! Be opened!

Codeswitching and Loanwords in the Gospel of Mark

Abstract

This article explores the social and literary functions of the loanwords and cases of codeswitching in the Gospel of Mark from a sociolinguistic perspective, as a means to understanding better the author and the discursive community for which he writes. Sociolinguistic concepts and definitions that affect the understanding of the different varieties of language will be discussed. These tools will then be applied to the Gospel of Mark to analyse significant aspects of its idiolect, especially those related to Mark's use of multilingualism. From this analysis conclusions are drawn that illuminate its idiolect from another angle, as well as the social actions that could be carried out by its author through the linguistic strategies that can be recognized from the study of its idiolect.

Keywords

Gospel of Mark, Sociolinguistics, Codeswitching, Aramaic, Koine Greek

Preprint Version

1 Introduction

‘Get up! (kumi¹) Open up!’ (efattá²). These are two imperatives in Aramaic that Mark puts into the mouth of Jesus in his Gospel which was written in Greek. Mark has surprisingly inserted Aramaic words in several places in his story, which he then translates into Greek, in order for them to be interpreted correctly. Mark’s Gospel also contains several words and expressions in Latin. What function do these changes of code (codeswitching) fulfil in his story? Why do they appear, when these changes are not commonly used in a written text?

This article aims to analyze one concrete aspect of the idiolect of the Gospel of Mark: his use of loanwords and codeswitching. It will be done from a sociolinguistic perspective to clarify some of the social functions that the author wants to develop in relation to his community. In order to do this, key concepts of sociolinguistics will be presented and later applied to Mark and conclusions will be then drawn about his story.

2 Key Concepts in Sociolinguistics

Sociolinguistics is concerned with the use of language within society and its social function. It also deals with different social factors and how they influence the use of the language.

In the field of bilingualism, the following specific language strategies and concepts are commonly used. They will be key tools in identifying the idiolect of the Gospel of Mark.

Idiolect is the unique and distinctive way that language is used by an individual and includes vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation, remembering that speech is a possession of the individual and the community³.

*Language contact*⁴ is the social phenomenon by which several languages come into contact and are affected in their phonology, as well as by semantic and linguistic loans.

Lexical borrowing is the direct transfer of an element from one language to another, where the original phonetic form adapts to the phonology of the receiving language without interpretation or translation⁵. Three major types can be distinguished⁶ namely, pure loanwords, loan shifts and creations. 1) *Pure loanwords* (form and meaning are copied completely, for example *hummus*) also include *loanblends* (one part of the compound is

¹ This is a corrected and expanded version of a previous article. Several parts of it were published previously in a Spanish journal (Delgado Gómez, Alfredo. Get up! Open up! Mark’s idiolect in the light of sociolinguistics. *Estudios Eclesiásticos: Journal of Theological and Canonical Research and Information*, 2018, 93: 29-86) which kindly agreed to this translation.

² Mk. 5.41. Get up! Transliterated and translated into Greek by Mark as: *κουμ ... ἔγειρε*, which would evoke the Aramaic verb *קומי*. Mk. 7.34. Be opened! Transliterated and translated by *εφφαθα ... διανοίχθητι*, which evokes the Aramaic imperative *פתח*.

³ Regarding idiolect cf. Higginbotham 2006.

⁴ Regarding language contact cf. Hickey 2010. The pioneer study was Weinreich 1953. About bilingualism and language contact cf. Appel and Muysken 1987: 165-166.

⁵ Borrowing is a completed process of language change, and a loanword/lexical borrowing is a particular type of such a change. Haspelmath 2009: 36 and 41. Loanwords can be divided into cultural borrowings (a new concept coming from outside), and core borrowings (which duplicate meanings for which a native word already exists). Myers-Scotton 2002: 41.

⁶ Haugen 1950: 213. Haugen underlines that classifications tell us little about the actual linguistic processes involved in lexical borrowing.

borrowed, the other one translated⁷). There are adapted loanwords, also called foreignisms⁸ (music in English from French *musique*) and not adapted (pizza). 2) *Loanshifts* (only the meaning is copied) fall into two subtypes (a) *loan translations* or *calques* (Spanish *rascacielos* from skyscraper) and (b) *semantic borrowings*, where only the meaning is copied (German *kontrollieren*, which originally only meant ‘check’, but is now also used in the sense of ‘having control over’, as in English). 3) *Creations*, involve the innovative use of native expressions to convey a foreign concept (the German *Umwelt* from the French *milieu*).

A change of code⁹ in the same statement is called *codeswitching*, whereby expressions from one language are introduced into another. It includes the insertion of isolated words, but also the inclusion of longer discourses¹⁰.

Two observations should be made. Firstly, there is no easy way of distinguishing, between loans and codeswitching. Loans appear as spontaneous codeswitching and then some of these switches are extended. Secondly it is possible for some loans to be so integrated into the recipient language that they are no longer identified as loanwords by the speakers. Some clues to distinguish them could be the following¹¹. 1) Loanwords are always words not lexical phrases, and they are unanalysable units in the recipient language. 2) Loanwords typically show various kinds of phonological and morphological adaptation, whereas code-switching by definition does not show any kind of adaptation¹². 3) A loanword is a word that can conventionally be used as part of the language. In particular, it can be used in situations where no code-switching occurs, e.g. in the speech of monolinguals¹³. 4) ‘Loans are more likely to be filling a ‘lexical gap’ in the host language, whereas code-switches tend simply to add themselves as a further option to the native equivalent’. 5) Loanwords are usually predictable, while codeswitching is not¹⁴.

We speak of *diglossia* when there are two different codes within a society with a clear functional separation¹⁵. It involves the use of two dialectal varieties of language one of which is associated with a high register and another with a low register in the colloquial domain. This phenomenon works socially, reinforcing the identification and membership of the speaker with a specific group. It is a property of the discursive, or informal, community rather than of the subject.

⁷ For example, the German *Backshop* ‘bakery’, with the English word ‘shop’ and ‘Back’ from the German *backen*, to bake.

⁸ Regarding loanwords adaptation cf. Uffmann 2015.

⁹ There are three specific perspectives in the study of codeswitching: psycholinguistics, the structural approach and sociolinguistics. The third is more interested in individual reasons of use, social norms and specific speech communities (power, prestige). Bullock and Toribio 2009: 14.

¹⁰ There are three types of codeswitching: intersentential, tag-switching and intrasentential. Poplack 1980: 615. Tags are freely moveable constituents which may be inserted almost anywhere in the sentence without fear of violating any grammatical rule. These tags could be discourse markers and interjections.

¹¹ Four characteristics are identified to differentiate loanwords from codeswitching and interference: multilingualism, adaptation, predictability, intentionality. Myers-Scotton 2002: 41.

¹² Grosjean 1995: 263

¹³ Haspelmath 2009: 40-41.

¹⁴ Gardner-Chloros 2010: 195-196.

¹⁵ Wardhaugh 2010: 89.

3 Previous observations

Several observations must be made before analyzing the multilingual functions of the Markan idiolect.

1. In the time of Jesus and Mark there was a multilingual situation both in Palestine and in the Roman Empire¹⁶. At least four languages were in general use in Palestine: Aramaic¹⁷ (or one of its regional and diachronic variations unknown to us), Greek as an international language (with its multiple variations), Latin as the language of the elite and Hebrew (in its biblical variants and the possible ancestor of the Rabbinic Hebrew¹⁸) as the language of the liturgy and of some groups such as Qumran.

2. It should be pointed out that Koine Greek was the *lingua franca*¹⁹ of the empire and not Latin, which was the language of the bureaucracy. The Roman troops communicated in Greek²⁰ as did Roman subjects²¹. In fact, Rome was not interested in foreign languages. When Latin appears, it is to send a message of authority and presence, such as on statues, inscriptions, etc. The function of Latin in Roman inscriptions fulfils a clear function: Rome wants remind itself of its power and presence: 'Rome rules here'.

3. The Gospel of Mark is a complex work in which the author has manipulated and reworked previous sources. Perhaps the clearest source is the story of the Passion²². The author also had access to oral and written sources including oral testimonies²³. Although it is not possible to access these sources²⁴, it can be said that they have influenced his style and writing, but unlike Titus Livius, Mark was skillful in integrating his sources into a coherent narrative, which makes them difficult to isolate²⁵. Some of the sources that it is possible to contrast include the books of the LXX, especially Isaiah, Psalms and Deuteronomy, from which Mark quotes.

4. It is not possible to develop here the characteristics of the Markan idiolect²⁶ and the peculiarities of his Koine Greek, 'a kind of Greek that was not normally used in literary composition, but stands closer to the vernacular²⁷'. Although the evangelist may have been bilingual, 'his Greek is entirely fluent and correct. The grammar of Mark is not faulty as much as it is substandard²⁸'.

¹⁶ On bilingualism in ancient society cf. Adams, Janse and Swain 2002. On the multilingual and diglossic situation of Palestine cf. Ong 2015. Watt 2000. Janse 2014a. Smelik 2010. Several articles in JGRChJ 12 (2016). A very interesting presentation in Spolsky 2014: 35-79. Buildings and its importance in Sawicki 2000.

¹⁷ Rochette 2014.

¹⁸ Both appear in Qumran texts. Sáenz-Badillos 1993: 163. Joosten 2010a.

¹⁹ *Lingua franca* is the use of a language as universal or widely extended that acts as a means of international communication. Meierkord 2006.

²⁰ The Roman army spoke in general Greek. Cf. Adams 2003: 606.

²¹ None of the edicts of the prefects of Egypt uses Latin. Latin was the language of bureaucracy and Greek was that of the family. It is a situation of diglossia. Eck 2003: 123. Flavius Josephus living in Rome, sponsored by the Flavian emperors, writes in Greek and not in Latin.

²² It is possible that Mark had a collection of controversies (Mk. 2.1-3.6) of parables (Mk. 4.1-35) and of two collections of miracles. Achtemeier 1972.

²³ There is no space here for a detailed analysis of several interesting topics as orality in Mark, memory studies, etc. The main interest in this article is the final text of Mark. Cf. Iverson 2009. Duling 2006.

²⁴ Burkett 2004. About the Aramaic sources of Mark cf. Casey 1998.

²⁵ Beard 2013: 76.

²⁶ On the Markan idiolect cf. Turner and Elliott 1993. Voelz 2014. Pryke 1978.

²⁷ Words like κράβατος (2.4) and κοράσιον (5.41) may indicate the colloquial quality of Mark's Greek. Joosten 2013: 40 and 44.

²⁸ Joosten 2013: 40.

But two characteristics of Mark's idiolect are important in relation to his use of loanwords and codeswitching. Firstly, there is the influence of the LXX²⁹ and consequently, the indirect influence of Hebrew and Aramaic³⁰, as well as the translation technique³¹ used in the LXX. The vocabulary, worldview and syntax of the LXX greatly influenced Mark and require us to be cautious when faced with assertions about his style³². Secondly, Mark uses a paratactic style.

The LXX exerts its linguistic influence on Mark in expressions, syntax³³ and vocabulary. Of the 11,099 words used by Mark, only 150 are not found in the LXX, and if the 60 proper names are removed, plus the loanwords from Latin and Aramaic, the number of words not found in the LXX is minimal³⁴. That is to say, the vocabulary of Mark is that of the books of the LXX. The Septuagint also influences Flavius Josephus and Philo, but does not affect their syntax³⁵, which is that of the Greek koine of high style. Josephus rewrites the LXX in his *Antiquities*, but he completely changes the syntax. He preserves the topic but not the style.

Linguistically, four expressions in the Gospel of Mark can be singled out that allude to constantly to the LXX: *καὶ ἐγένετο*³⁶, *καὶ εὐθύς*, *καθὼς γέγραπται* and the repeated use of *καί*³⁷. The expression *καὶ ἐγένετο* (translation of the Hebrew *wayyehi*, Mk. 1.9) is not found in non-biblical Greek³⁸. The expression *καθὼς γέγραπται* is a typical formula for citing the scriptures (2 Kgs. 14.6 LXX). The expression *καὶ εὐθύς* (42x) is used in the LXX to translate *wehinneh*. The repeated use of *καί* at the beginning of the sentences reveals the influence of the LXX. These are four clear semantic and syntactic indicators that point to a dependence of the LXX. One can also point to the expression 'answered and said' (3.33, 6.37) and the high frequency of *ἰδοῦ* (7x) as a reflection of the translation of *hinne*.

However, the most distinctive feature of Mark's idiolect is his paratactic style, linking clauses with *καί* instead of using other conjunctions³⁹. According to Metzger, 80 of the 88 sections of Mark begin with *καί* (410 of the 678 vv. begin with *καί*). Likewise, 64% of the sentences begin with *καί*⁴⁰. As an example, in the first chapter of Mark, 33 of the 38 sentences begin with *καί*. The frequency of 'sentence-initial *καί*' according to the statistics is very close to that found in Gen., 1 Chron. and 1 Mac. This repeated use is

²⁹ Lee 1985.

³⁰ Joosten 2010b. A good study with extensive bibliography is Byun 2017. The influence of Hebrew and Aramaic on LXX is fundamentally on the meaning of words and not so much on their signifiers. Tov 2006: 461.

³¹ Dines and Knibb 2004: 117-128. Olofsson 2009.

³² The Koine Greek of the LXX and Mark is not the same, due to the evolution of this language between the third century BCE and the first century CE.

³³ Lee speaks of cases of grammaticalization by the influence of the LXX in Mark in the communication verbs (*εἶπεν*, *ἀποκριθεὶς*), in the verbs of movement (*ἐλθὼν*, *καταλιπὼν*), in postural verbs, in certain conjunctions (*ὅτι* 102x; *ἵνα* 64x) and in adverbs (*τότε* 6x; *εὐθύς* 41x). Lee 2012: 252-281. The syntax of Mark is very poor in particles: *ἄρα* 2x; *μὲν δέ* 3x; *οὖν* 3x, while in John 200x appears. For Reiser the Semitisms have no influence on Mark at the level of syntax or style. Reiser 1984. On the Semitisms in the NT cf. Black 1988. In Mark, Rieger 1984. For the influence of LXX in the NT cf. McLay 2003.

³⁴ Swete 1898: xlv.

³⁵ The expression *καὶ ἐγένετο* appears 21x in Philo and 3x in Josephus. *καὶ εὐθύς* doesn't appear in Josephus but 9x in Philo.

³⁶ Lars Hartman has stressed that Mark's style tries to imitate the historical narratives of the OT by using expressions such as *καὶ ἐγένετο* and *ἀποκριθεὶς εἶπεν* (3.33; 6.37). Hartman 2010: 95.

³⁷ Decker 2013: 47. Recently Baum 2016.

³⁸ Marcus 2000: 169. Also Maloney 1981: 81-86.

³⁹ *καί* is a complex particle. It can mean parataxis, logical consequence, temporal indication. Decker 2013: 47 and Turner and Elliott 1993: 23. About *καί* cf. Thrall 1962. Titrud 1992.

⁴⁰ Metzger 1951: 48. None of Luke's sections starts with *καί*.

surely the effect of the influence of the LXX and not so much of the Hebrew⁴¹. There is also a frequent use of καὶ εὐθὺς⁴² that functions as a discourse marker signaling the beginning of a new episode. This highly paratactic style separates Mark from the high Greek style, which makes frequent use of subordinate clauses and participles. Markan sentences are surprisingly short in comparison to the high Greek style and are a deliberate choice on the part of the author who is capable of a higher register⁴³.

4 The use of Hebrew, Aramaic and Latin in Mark

A very important characteristic of Mark is the influences of the Hebrew, Aramaic⁴⁴ and Latin languages and the use he makes of them. They will be developed later. In this regard Martin Hengel points out that there is no document of antiquity like the Gospel of Mark with so much Aramaic and Hebrew present⁴⁵. It is surprising that this occurs to such an extent in a literary text⁴⁶, since codeswitching is usually a characteristic of oral language. The high frequency of these loanwords in Mark's Gospel could be a confirmation of the oral tradition which lay behind it, an aspect that has not been addressed until now in the research related to 'Orality and the Gospels'. In Mark there are cases of loanwords and codeswitching with both languages, which could be an indication of his self-identity and an additional communicative resource⁴⁷. The following are instances of loanwords and codeswitching, both semantic and grammatical⁴⁸.

4.1 Hebrew

Several Hebrew theophoric names can be identified such as John (26x), Jesus, Elijah (9x), Isaiah, Jacob, Israel, Matthew, Joseph, Joses, Zebedee, Simon⁴⁹; proper names such as Levi, Judah, Abiathar, Jairus, Miriam, Salome and placenames such as Bethphage, Bethany, Bethsaida, Gethsemani, Gennesaret, Magdala, Jordan, etc.

Examples of Hebrew foreignisms include the words Pharisees and Sadducees. Examples of semantic calque are the words Christ⁵⁰ (Dan. 9.25), and the expressions: 'son

⁴¹ Decker 2013: 66 and 48.

⁴² The word εὐθὺς appears 42x. Decker 1997. Schupbach 2013. Ellingworth 1978.

⁴³ Mark knows how to write with long phrases and with several subordinates (3.14-19; 7.2-5; 13.14-16). The longest sentence of Mark contains 84 words and the next 52, with paratactic unions mostly.

⁴⁴ Fitzmyer 1997.

⁴⁵ Hengel 1983: 243. Black 1954.

⁴⁶ It is not possible to present here the complexity of the bilingual inscriptions, coins, ossuaries and epitaphs. Usually they are twin texts with the same content presented in parallelism. Cf. Hengel 1996 and Fitzmyer 1970.

⁴⁷ Watt 2013: 19.

⁴⁸ Grammatical Semitisms are difficult to isolate due to the influence of the LXX. A case could be Mk. 4.8. Geiger 2014. Silva 1975.

⁴⁹ Knowing that etymology does not determine the meaning of a word, some of the possible translations of these Hebrew names are presented. They are taken from Fitzmyer, a great specialist. Fitzmyer 2006. John (Yahweh shows his favor), Matthew (gift of Yahweh), Elijah (Yahweh is God), Isaiah (Yahweh is salvation). Simon (a diminutive, God has heard). Jacob (God protect us) Joseph ('The Lord add' more children to those already born). Joses is an abbreviation of Joseph. Miriam (height, summit). Salome (Peace). Abiathar (The father gives generously). Jairus (May he enlighten). Zebedee (from Aramaic *zabday* or Hebrew *zebadya*, means gift of Yah). Bethany (house of Ananias, also of the poor or of affliction), Bethphage (house of figs) and Bethsaida (house of fishing or hunting) these last two are Aramaic words for Fitzmyer). Magdala (Tower), Jordan (the one that goes down).

⁵⁰ In Mark it means anointed, king. In the Hellenistic world it would mean buttered; something like rubbed, used as an ointment or balm. Twice the word Christ is object of an apposition (14.61 and 15.32). They are explanations, if not direct translations. Explanations in direct speech, principally for the reader.

of man⁵¹ (Num. 23.19; Dan. 7.13-14), ‘the abomination of desolation’ (Mk. 13.14; Dan. 11.31; 12.11; 9.27), ‘son of David’ (10.47-48; 12.35; 1 Kgs. 1.13; 2.1; 1 Chron. 29.22), ‘children of the nuptial hall’ (Mk. 2.19), ‘what do we have to do with you?’ (Mk. 1.24; Judg. 11.12; 2 Kgs. 3.13), ‘the Holy One of God’ (2 Kgs. 4.9), ‘House of God’ (Mk. 2.26), ‘corner stone’ (12:10; Psalm 118:22). The metaphors constructed with the words ‘son’ and ‘house’ are deeply Hebraic and their translations into Greek are an example of semantic calque, which could only be understood in a Judeo-Hellenistic context⁵².

4.2 Aramaic

Loanwords found in Mark are: *πάσχα* (14.1,12), *σάββατον*⁵³ and *σατανᾶς* (1.13, 3.23), words that also come from the LXX⁵⁴. Other Aramaic words are placenames such as Golgotha (Γολγοθᾶ), Gehenna⁵⁵ (Γέεννα), and proper names such as Beelzebub (Βεελζεβούλ), Bartholomew (Βαρθολομαῖον), Barabbas (Βαραββᾶς son of the father⁵⁶!), Thaddeus (Θαδδαῖον) and Thomas (Θωμᾶς).

Examples of tag-codeswitching with Aramaic words are⁵⁷: *ῥαββί*⁵⁸ and *ῥαββουεῖ*⁵⁹ and *ὠσαννά*, which are not translated in the Gospel. The word *ὠσαννά*⁶⁰ (11.9,10) is a transliteration into Greek of a Hebrew loanword that was accepted in Aramaic. The word *ἀμήν*⁶¹ (14x), appears always as a case of intrasentential (in fact, intracause) codeswitching: ‘ἀμήν λέγω ὑμῖν’, without translation.

⁵¹ For a literary explanation of the literary functions of the title son of the man in Mark cf. Fowler 1991: 129 and 131. In p. 77 Fowler affirms: The ‘amen’, ‘whoever’, and ‘Son of man’ statements are the clearest expressions we have of the norms and standards of judgment of the narrator of Mark's Gospel.

⁵² The metaphor ‘dog’ (7.27), coming from Hebrew and Aramaic is another example. A very interesting analyses of the Greek background of *υἱός* as a noun of relationship in Hogeterp 2011: 186-190.

⁵³ Mk. 1.21; 2.23.24.27 (2x).28; 3.2,4; 6.2; 16.1,2.

⁵⁴ These could be examples of words incorporated in the recipient language of the discursive community of Mark, due to their presence in LXX and their wide use. The words *σανδαλιον* (6.9) and *ἀγγαρευω* (15.21) come from the Persian. The word *γαζα* that appears in *γαζοφυλάκιον* (12.41,43) also comes from the Persian but *γαζοφυλάκιον* appears in the LXX. The word *κραβαττος* (2:4) comes from the Macedonia-Illyrian. All of them were integrated in the Greek of that time and surely not recognized as loanwords by the community. Beekes and Beek 2010: 1305, 9, 1894 and 766-767.

⁵⁵ Γέεννα (9.43.45.47) is the transcription of the Aramaic word *gēhinnām*. It comes from the Hebrew *gēhinnom*. It means the Valley of Hinnom, a valley near Jerusalem (2 Kgs. 23.20; Jer. 7.31). Later it will designate the place of eternal punishment (4 Esd. 7.36).

⁵⁶ This word appears 3x. Unlike Bartimaeus, this name is not translated. Maybe the author does not want to mislead his audience.

⁵⁷ It is not easy to distinguish if they are Hebrew loanwords in Aramaic or Aramaic words properly. Both 2013b.

⁵⁸ Mk. 9.5; 11.21; 14.45. For Cohen, at this time, it is a popular designation for someone of high standing. Cohen 1981-1982: 9.

⁵⁹ Mk. 10.51. This word was found twice in the D and Z manuscripts of the Targum to Gen. 44.18 of the Cairo Genizah. Díez Macho 1988: 338-339, 558.

⁶⁰ Mk. 11.9,10. It is a foreignism. The root *שׁוּ* is not attested in Aramaic, although the form *שׁוּ* appears in an Aramaic text from Qumran (4Q243 16.2) and the root *שׁוּ* appears in another Aramaic text, both associated with a cry of greeting or homage. Fitzmyer 1987: 112. The Greek word *ὠσαννά*, transliterates the Aramaic word *ܫܘܫܢܐ* *hosanna*, which is an adaptation of the Hebrew expression *הוֹשִׁיעֵנו הוֹשִׁיעֵנו* *hosia-nna* that only appears in Ps. 118.25. In the original Hebrew *hosia-nna* was a request for help. The meaning of the expression evolved to become, in its Aramaic use in Israel, an exclamation of praise. See Pope 1992. It must be remembered that the meaning of a word is given by its use. About the process of semantic change cf. Campbell 2013: 221-246.

⁶¹ Mk. 3.28; 8.12; 9.1,41; 10.15.29; 11.23; 12.43; 13.30; 14.9,18,25,30. Lee defines the word as Aramaic. Lee 2012: 254. The Aramaic word *ܐܡܝܢ* is a verb, passive participle. The Greek word *ἀμήν* in Jesus' direct speech is an adapted loanword from Hebrew into Aramaic, and then transliterated and adapted into Greek. Cf. Fitzmyer 2006: 536-537.

There are a number of instances of intrasentential codeswitching of repetition and translation⁶², that is to say, phrases where the Aramaic expression is translated into its Greek equivalent in the same sentence; several of them are introduced with the expressions ὁ ἐστίν (4x) or with ὁ ἐστίν μεθερμηνευόμενον (3x). They are the following: ὁ υἱὸς Τιμαίου Βαρτιμαῖος⁶³ (10.46); Βοανηργές, ὁ ἐστίν υἱὸν βροντῆς⁶⁴ (3.17), ταλιθα κουμ, ὁ ἐστίν μεθερμηνευόμενον τὸ κοράσιον, σοὶ λέγω, ἔγειρε (5.41); κορβᾶν⁶⁵, ὁ ἐστίν δῶρον (7.11); εφραθα, ὁ ἐστίν διανοίχθητι (7.34); γέενναν, εἰς τὸ πῦρ τὸ ἄσβεστον (9.43); αββα⁶⁶ ὁ πατήρ (14.36); Γολγοθᾶν τόπον, ὁ ἐστίν μεθερμηνευόμενον Κρανίου Τόπος (15.22); ελωι ελωι λεμα σαβαχθανι; ὁ ἐστίν μεθερμηνευόμενον ὁ θεός μου ὁ θεός μου, εἰς τί ἐγκατέλιπές με; (15.34⁶⁷); παρασκευῆ ὁ ἐστίν προσάββατον (15.42). Especially significant are the three complete sentences: ἐφραθά⁶⁸; ταλιθα κουμ⁶⁹ (both in stories of miracles) and the expression ελωι ελωι λεμα σαβαχθανι⁷⁰ which is the Greek transliteration of an Aramaic psalm.

⁶² About repetition code-switching, cf. Gumperz 1982: 78, where he talks about reiteration. Harjunpää and Mäkilähde 2016. Finlayson and Slabbert 1997: 394. The important thing is the change, not the reference value of the word, since it does not change.

⁶³ Bartimaeus (son of Timaeus). It is something unusual. It is an example of codemixing within the same name with an Aramaic (bar) and a Greek (Timaeus, a name that means valuable, honest). Thomas (twin). Bartholomew (son of Talmai 2 Sam. 3.3). Thaddaeus (brave). Satan (accuser). Lee 2012: 267. For Hengel, Thaddaeus (tadda'j) is probably a short form of Theodotus and Bartholomew derives from (bar) Ptolemaios. Hengel 1996: 30. Bartimaeus and Bartholomew are two cases of loanblends (hybrid borrowings which consist of partly borrowed material and partly native material).

⁶⁴ A play on words with βοαν, scream. Its etymology is not clear. It is surprising, on the other hand, that this Aramaic support is remembered and that the Aramaic name of Peter, Cephas, is not remembered. (Gal. 2.9; 1 Cor. 1.12; Jn. 1.42). Peter, rock and Sons of Thunder are both hyperbolic epithets. Boane may represent bēnē, the Hebrew word for 'sons of', but the rest of Mark's transliteration is puzzling, since *rges* does not correspond to the Hebrew or Aramaic words for 'thunder'; the nearest Hebrew is *r'm*. Other possibilities are that *rges* renders a word for excitement (*rgz*), for commotion and anger (*rgš*), or for quaking (*r's*). Dahl suggests that it could also hint that the brothers will be exposed to the eschatological thunderstorm, as will Jesus himself (cf. 10.38–40). The suggestion of a positive meaning is slightly supported by the similar name of an ancient Jewish town, Bēnē Bēraq = 'sons of lightning', which like most town names probably has a positive nuance. Marcus 2000: 264.

⁶⁵ This Hebrew word (meaning animal sacrificed to God) was received in Aramaic, meaning gift and appears in the Mishnah (where its meaning is vote) and in Flavius Josephus. The meaning in Mark is 'vote'. Zeitlin 1968. In Aramaic it has appeared in an inscription. Fitzmyer 1959.

⁶⁶ ἄββά and Βαρτιμαῖος, with their translations, are two cases of repetition of tag-sentential codeswitching.

⁶⁷ Mark do not repeat the literal translation of the LXX. ὁ θεὸς ὁ θεός μου πρόσχες μοι ἵνα τί ἐγκατέλιπές με.

⁶⁸ It was debated whether it was a Hebrew word (Rabinowitz) or Aramaic, the latter being the one that has been demonstrated, due to its appearance as a gloss in the Targum Neofiti Gen. 3.7. Marcus 2000: 362. Horton 1986.

⁶⁹ It is not possible to detail the problems of textual criticism on this word, with two options being κουμ or κουμι (fem.). Our ignorance of the dialectal variant of the Aramaic spoken by Jesus, as well as the dialect variant that Mark would know, oblige us to be cautious.

⁷⁰ For Buth it would be a possible example of a divine voice, *bat qol*, speaking from heaven. It would form an inclusion with baptism, where Jesus is recognized as a child of God. Buth 2013a: 414.

4.3 Latin

There are also many Latin loanwords and examples of code mixing between Latin and Greek⁷¹. The extent of them is surprising in a first-century text, since most of the Latin loanwords appear in texts of subsequent centuries⁷². In Mark Latin is used for military and administrative terms, currencies, measures. Its use is confined to nouns⁷³. Van Iersel⁷⁴ identifies three groups. Firstly, words that are adapted transcriptions of Latin words (foreignisms): Καίσαρος caesar⁷⁵ (12.16-17), μοδιον modius (4.21), σπεκουλατωρ speculator⁷⁶ (6.27), δηναριον denarius (12.15), ξεστης sextarius (7.4), κηνσος census (12.14), φραγελλω fragellare (15.15), κεντυρίων centurio (15.39.44.45), κοδραντης quadrans (12.42), πραιτώριον praetorium (15.16), λεγιων legio (5.9,15), κράβαττον grabatus⁷⁷ (2.4,9,11), οὐαί⁷⁸ vae (13.17). Secondly, literal translations of Greek words (semantic calque), συμβολιον (consilium 3.6; 15.1), πυγμή (pugno or pugillo 7.3) and Greek words with a Latin meaning (semantic borrowings) such as ἔχω (11.32). Thirdly, transpositions of Latin expressions into unknown Greek word combinations (semantic calque), τὸ ἱκανὸν ποιέω (satisfacere 15.15), ῥάπισμασιν λαμβάνω (verberibus accipere 14.65), ὁδὸν ποιέω (viam facere 2.23), ἐσχάτως ἔχω (ultimum habere 5.23), τίθημι τὰ γόνατα (genua ponere 15.19), κατακρίνω θανάτω (capitae damnare⁷⁹ 10.33). Two Latin names, Pilate and Rufus⁸⁰, appear, and Mark, the title of the Gospel, is itself a Latin name⁸¹.

There are two significant cases of intrasentential codeswitching of repetition and translation into Latin, namely: λεπτὰ δύο, ὃ ἐστὶν κοδραντης (12.42) and τῆς αὐλῆς, ὃ ἐστὶν πραιτώριον (15.16).

Van Iersel adds two more examples. Firstly, the position of the verb in the phrase and the place of the noun in relation to the pronoun that belongs to it. Secondly, the use of ἵνα in the non-final sense, of the Latin *ut* after verbs of speaking⁸².

⁷¹ Rochette 2010. Adams 2003. Filos 2014. Lorenzetti 2014.

⁷² Dickey 2003.

⁷³ 'Greek loanwords of Latin origin refer almost exclusively to civil and military administration and are confined to nouns'. Janse 2014b: 123. Schirru points out that Latin loanwords belong to the civil and administrative world, as well as military and that this language was seen as the language of the dominators. Schirru 2013: 327.

⁷⁴ Van Iersel 1998: 33-35.

⁷⁵ Also the town Καισάρεια τῆς Φιλίππου, Caesarea Philippi.

⁷⁶ It refers to a personal guard. The word appears in Tacitus, *Historiae* I.24-25; II.73.

⁷⁷ From the Latin grabatus. It could also be a loan from a Macedonia-Illyrian word for oak. The word would have been adopted independently by Greeks and Romans. Beekes and Beek 2010: 766. The Latin versions translate it as grabattus.

⁷⁸ It appears in the LXX 60x.

⁷⁹ In the Latin versions these Greek words are translated by the Latin equivalents indicated. However ξεστης is translated by urceus, κηνσος by tributum and πυγμή is omitted. Of the expressions only τίθημι τὰ γόνατα is translated by the Latin expression expected.

⁸⁰ It is a common Latin name for slaves.

⁸¹ Hengel 2008: 142.

⁸² These are cases of language loanwords and grammaticalization. Matras 2007. Eckardt 2006.

5 Functions of Multilingualism in Mark

Having identified the use of loanwords and codeswitching in Mark, it is particularly important to understand the function of these loanwords, as well as the function fulfilled by codeswitching within the Gospel. It is not a case of language mixture or interference, that is, they do not result from unconscious or psychological use of language⁸³. Nor are they a result of confusion by the author at the time of writing, as the explanatory expressions ὁ ἔστιν⁸⁴ and ὁ ἔστιν μεθερμηνευόμενον⁸⁵ indicate. It is clear that these loanwords and cases of codeswitching play a definite role.

It is surprising that the writings of Paul, Flavius Josephus and Matthew, all of them multilingual, have few cases of codeswitching⁸⁶. Likewise there are very few Aramaic words in the LXX⁸⁷. In this sense it is noteworthy that there are no Greek loanwords in the Qumran texts⁸⁸, nor any from Latin. Their absence responds to an awareness of the identity of that community and equally reinforces their identity⁸⁹. It contrasts with the multitude of Greek, Latin and Aramaic loanwords in the Mishnah and in the Targum⁹⁰. Therefore, the social function of their presence in Mark must be analyzed. This analysis is difficult, however because of our lack of knowledge about the author or the historical circumstances of his community⁹¹.

⁸³ It is not a case of interference. Interference is a term to refer to errors made in the language that has been learned (L2) by the influence of the native language (L1). Sometimes using an expression from L1 leads to an error. In these cases, it is considered that what has been learned, hinders what is going to be learned.

⁸⁴ Fowler 1991: 107-109. About this expression cf. Robertson 1914: 713-714.

⁸⁵ For Moule, it is an explanatory participle rather than a periphrastic construction. Moule 1953: 17.

⁸⁶ Feldman underlines this absence. Feldman 1984: 832. About the Greek literary language of Josephus cf. Redondo 2000. About latinisms in Josephus cf. Ward 2007. About Semitisms in Matthew cf. Davies and Allison 1988: 80-85 and 73.

⁸⁷ It is greatly surprising given that the mother tongue of the Jews of Egypt was Aramaic. Joosten 2010b: 9.

⁸⁸ Cotton 2000: 325. With the exception of the Copper Scroll (3Q315) which has greek four loanwords (peristyle and amphora) and cases of script-switching (greek letters in a hebrew text).

⁸⁹ The absence of Greek loanwords in the rest of the Dead Sea Scrolls is a theologically motivated choice, a conscious refusal of interaction with a foreign culture. García Martínez 2007: 167.

⁹⁰ On Greek and Latin loanwords in Rabbinic Literature cf. Krauss 1899. Heijmans 2014. Krivoruchko 2012. Sperber 1984. Fischel 2008.

⁹¹ 'In situations of intense language contact, speakers tend to develop some mechanism for equating 'similar' concepts and categories across languages'. Heine and Kuteva 2005: 4.

5.1 Function of the Koine Greek influenced by the LXX

To understand the function of codeswitching in Mark, it is important to begin with an understanding of the author's choice of his base language and only then is it possible to comprehend the reason why he makes these code changes⁹². Mark writes in Greek and not in Aramaic as did Bar Kokhba⁹³, nor in Hebrew as in the writings of Qumran⁹⁴, nor in Latin, the language of power and of the bureaucracy of Rome and the elite. All of these were possible languages he could have used. Instead Mark writes in the *lingua franca* of the empire, Koine Greek.

Therefore, for Mark, the function of his choice of Koine Greek with its low register and simple style was to address his Christian community and maybe the Hellenistic Jewish community (God-fearing Jews of the diaspora) who in the first century could be part of the lower classes of society and not part of the elite. The semantic, syntactic, intertextual and narrative references in Mark's Gospel to the LXX, link the narrative to the LXX and to its worldview. Mark chose to link his story to the history of Israel, a story that appears intertwined in the books of the LXX, and as an example of it, he made an explicit reference with Isaiah in his prologue (Mk. 1.2-3).

It is important to note that Mark's simple Koine style that imitates the LXX was rejected by the Greco-Roman elite⁹⁵. An analysis of works published in Greek⁹⁶ throughout the first century (few of which have survived⁹⁷), shows that the language of the Gospel of Mark was definitely among those of simpler style. In the second century, Philostratus, Lucian of Samosata and Celsus were disparaging of the low stylistic level of the Gospels. For Celsus the Gospels were of a low quality⁹⁸, which prevented them from being considered biographical works. He described them as non-historical and even fictional (*πλάσματα*⁹⁹). Matthew and Luke also considered Mark's style was poor, and that their own was an improvement¹⁰⁰. The fathers of the Church apologized for the low style of the Gospels¹⁰¹, whilst their own style although varied, tended towards a high register¹⁰².

⁹² According to the 'Markedness Model', there is an unmarked choice (Greek), a code which is expected in the specific context. Quite often, in fact, local solidarity requires the use of a non-prestige language or variety (in this case Aramaic or Latin); or it may require a mixing of two languages. All language choices, marked and unmarked, contribute to the relationship between the speakers. Myers-Scotton 1993.

⁹³ There were eight letters in Aramaic, three in Hebrew and two in Greek in the cave of letters. Surely none was written or signed by Bar Kokhba. This movement knows the Greek as it's evidenced by the letters written in Greek addressed to Bar Kokhba, Yadin P 52 and P 59. Schäfer 2003: 144. Doering 2012: 78 and 499.

⁹⁴ There are numerous texts in Aramaic in Qumran that surely were not written in the community, but were copies brought from outside. See a classification in Dimant 2007: 200-201.

⁹⁵ At the moment in which Mark writes, the opinion of the Greco-Roman society about Judaism was negative. There were many different opinions and several stages to be highlighted, but the Greco-Roman world in general despised Judaism. This is the conclusion of several works dealing with the Greco-Roman attitude towards Judaism: Bar-Kochva 2010. Feldman 1993: 84-106. Fernández Marcos 2012.

⁹⁶ Dihle 1994. Easterling and Knox 1985. Lesky 1999. Hose and Schenker 2015.

⁹⁷ Two thirds of the papyri discovered in Oxyrhynchus belong to unknown works and authors of classical antiquity. Bowman, Coles, Gonis, Obbink and Parsons 2007: 9.

⁹⁸ 'I have said this in reply to the criticism of Celsus and others that the scriptures have a mean style, which appears to be put in the shade by the brilliance of a literary composition'. Origen, *Cels.* VI.2 and I.62.

⁹⁹ Origen, *Cels.* II.13.26. Cook 2000: 26.

¹⁰⁰ The style of 1 Pet. is more complex than Paul's, Paul's is more complex than Luke's, and this is more complex than Mark's. For Wifstrand, Mark is more representative of the usual popular language. Wifstrand 2005: 19.

¹⁰¹ 'For in them there was no power of speaking or of giving an ordered narrative by the standards of Greek dialectical or rhetorical arts ...they have been suspected of making use of a method similar to that of philosophers who are leaders of some particular sect'. Origen, *Cels.* I.62.

¹⁰² Bentein 2015: 469.

5.2 Functions of Loanwords and Codeswitching

Before analyzing the functions of codeswitching in Mark in his use of Aramaic, Hebrew and Latin, it is worth remembering that loanwords and codeswitching can fulfil several functions.

Firstly, loanwords can serve a number of different functions. They can fill a lexical gap or achieve a special effect such as sounding more polite or of a higher status due to the prestige of the donor language; engaging with a specific social dialect; altering the meaning associated with an idea; avoiding a native equivalent because it could sound too direct, avoiding negative connotations; having a euphemistic function; avoiding homonym.

Secondly, there are a great variety of psychological, social and conversational reasons to explain the use of codeswitching¹⁰³. These include filling a linguistic gap, expressing ethnic identity, achieving a linguistic intention, emphasizing something, affirming power, declaring solidarity, maintaining a certain neutrality in spaces where two codes are used, etc. Codeswitching acts as a marker of belonging to a group and generates solidarity with it¹⁰⁴. It is not a random or meaningless change¹⁰⁵.

Specific functions of code-switches in writing might include the following: quotation; emphasis; clarification/elaboration; repetition; commentary; exclamation; directives; change of topic; change of interlocutor; parenthesis; idiomatic expression; symmetric alternation; triggered switch; stylistic; lexical need; interjection; expletive, 'description, evocation of cultural associations, instruction; request, wordplay, metalinguistic, naming¹⁰⁶.

In this regard, it can be added that codeswitching can also evoke negative nuances. Social codeswitching is often underestimated, because it indicates vagueness¹⁰⁷. People perceive it as a degeneration of the language. Aristotle, who was well aware of the different varieties of style (λέξις) that could be adopted and gave precise indications that distinguish one style from another¹⁰⁸, pointed out that one indication of good style was purity of language (ἐλληνίζειν), through which it avoids barbarism and solecism¹⁰⁹, that is to say avoids using expressions of other languages.

¹⁰³ Gardner-Chloros 2009: 42-43. Myers-Scotton 1993.

¹⁰⁴ Bullock and Toribio 2009: 4 and 10.

¹⁰⁵ Gardner-Chloros 2009: 15.

¹⁰⁶ Gardner-Chloros and Weston 2015: 186. Mullen 2015: 221. Callahan adds: 1) referential; 2) vocatives; 3) expletives (taboo); 4) quotation; 5) commentary and repetition; 6) set phrases, tags, and exclamations; 7) discourse markers; and 8) directives. Callahan 2004: 70. And Gumperz proposes: quotation, addressee specification, interjection, reiteration, message qualification and personalization v. objectification. Gumperz 1982: 75-84.

¹⁰⁷ Bullock and Toribio 2009: 1.

¹⁰⁸ Aristotle, *Rhet.* III.1407a.19-20. Quintilian also refers to the *Latinitas*. Quintilian, *Inst.* I.4.1.

¹⁰⁹ Lucian, *Soleocista* 23. In Antiquity these barbarisms were considered a blemish. Norden 1898: 60-63.

5.3 *The Function of Aramaic in Mark*

The functions developed by the loanwords and the cases of codeswitching of Latin, Hebrew and Aramaic in Mark are different. In this section we analyze the social functions of the use of Aramaic in Mark and in the following sections those of Hebrew and Latin.

5.3.1 *Previous observations*

In the first place it must be remembered that Greek and Aramaic¹¹⁰ experienced a prolonged situation of language contact, Palestine being a clear example of this¹¹¹.

Secondly, it should be recalled that both cases of Aramaic loanwords, and cases of whole sentence codeswitching appear in Mark. The switches of code are by far the more important.

Thirdly, some of these Aramaic words were undoubtedly known and used by the community since words such as *hosanna*, *rabbi*, *amen* and *abba* appear in other texts¹¹² (Jn. 1.51, Gal. 4.6 and Rom 8.15). However, other Aramaic words have to be explained to Mark's audience (even *abba* has to be translated), which indicates that a majority of his community would not have known Aramaic¹¹³.

The final observation concerns the translation and the word order. It can be said that in this case 'the order of factors alters the effect'. Mark's discourse is developed in Greek and suddenly there is a change of code to Aramaic. The Aramaic phrase or word (e.g. *ἐφραθά*) is then followed by a translation into Greek (*διανοίχθητι*), this translation having been introduced by a formula (*ὃ ἐστίν*) that allows both phrases to be connected, and which makes the translation explicit¹¹⁴. The Aramaic appears, in general, next to its Greek translation and the use of the Aramaic word as a kind of magic formula is therefore avoided¹¹⁵. From a literary point of view, this translation gives the reader privileged information¹¹⁶ and places the author in the superior position of being a translator, interpreter and guarantor of a tradition that goes back to Jesus¹¹⁷.

5.3.2 *General functions*

1) Many of these Aramaic words appear on the lips of Jesus in direct discourse¹¹⁸, and in so doing Mark seeks to enhance Jesus' words. The presence of the Aramaic therefore has a positive function. These words take the author's audience by surprise and enhance the performance and prominence of Jesus in the story. Several of them are very important words in the Gospel. They are neither random nor meaningless. Jesus heals two people using Aramaic imperatives and on both occasions that Jesus addresses God he does so in Aramaic. These Aramaic words characterize both Jesus and the narrator, as

¹¹⁰ An excellent presentation of the complex situation of Aramaic is found in Smelik 1995: 1-40. Gzella 2015.

¹¹¹ Bubeník 1989. Bubeník 2014. Silva 1980. About the loanwords in areas of language contact cf. Field 2002.

¹¹² Also Paul quotes the prayer '*maranatha*', 'Come Lord Jesus' (1 Cor. 16.22, see Rev. 22.20) and in Revelation appears '*nai, amen*' (Rev. 1.7).

¹¹³ It seems some Jewish traditions have to be explained as well, as it appears in Mk. 7.

¹¹⁴ The contrary situation in Jn. 19.17: 'the place of the Skull (which in Aramaic is called Golgotha)'.

¹¹⁵ Cf. Lucian of Samosata, who talks about foreign barbarous words (*ῥῆσις βαρβαρικῆ*) used by healers. Lucian, *Alexander* 9. Lucian, *Soleocista* 9 and 31. Philostratus talks about 'dark words' (*καί τι ἀφανῶς ἐπειπόν*). Philostratus, *Vit. Apoll.* 4.45. Other examples appear in Bultmann 1931: 227. Cf. Dibelius 1919: 46-47.

¹¹⁶ Fowler 1991: 109.

¹¹⁷ This translation codeswitching gives additional authority to the author. Davidson 2003.

¹¹⁸ This change from the aorist to the historical present creates emphasis.

native Aramaic speakers. In fact ‘codeswitching can provide different ‘voices’ to the same speaker¹¹⁹’.

2) These cases of repetition codeswitching slow down the narrative and therefore give the reader time to assimilate new information¹²⁰. They are signaled by the use of the present tense (ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν, ὃ ἐστὶν μεθερμηνευόμενον, ὃ ἐστὶν). Several of them are occasional departures which move the reader from the time of the telling to the time of the story. They cause emphasis and surprise and make the narrative more vivid. Being unexpected they attract the attention of the reader. The pioneer of information theory Shannon said that ‘the more unexpected a linguistic element is, the greater the amount of information¹²¹’. If this assertion is applied to the Semitisms of Mark, it implies that they convey a lot of unexpected and surprising information.

3) These Aramaic words give reliability¹²² to the narrator and the historical intention of the Gospel¹²³. The author as translator and transmitter is placed as a reliable witness and interpreter of the tradition, someone important in his community. Their appearance reminds the chain of witnesses and reinforces the Christian identity of the community. These Semitisms reinforce the bonding of the community with Jesus and his followers and at the same time unite it as a community.

4) The use of Aramaic words and their translation into Greek, together with his anonymity, and the open ending of his story, reinforce the author’s identity¹²⁴ and places him in a privileged position as an interpreter. He knows the original words of Jesus and situates himself as a translator and privileged interpreter of a message that he leaves open.

5) These Aramaic words and phrases strengthen the community’s identity as followers of Jesus. The recourse and remembrance of these prayers and phrases of Jesus reinforce the identity of his community. They make sense only to those inside it. That is why some of the words are translated and others are not, even when there is a translation available in the LXX¹²⁵.

And finally, his Semitisms will distance him from the Greco-Roman elite that would perceive these barbarisms as confirmation of being in front of a strange and foreign text¹²⁶. Both Matthew and Luke would eliminate these Arameisms in their desire to improve on Mark’s style.

5.3.3 Concrete Cases

The respective function of some specific loanwords and switches of code are the following.

Several loanwords (Sabbath, Satan, Passover) do not play a significant role in the Gospel. These words were originally loanwords, but by the year 70 CE they had definitely been assimilated by the receiving community and had become part of its vocabulary.

¹¹⁹ Gardner-Chloros 2009: 77. ‘Codeswitching helps create the identity one wishes to be seen as having in a particular set of circumstances’. Wardhaugh and Fuller 2015: 99.

¹²⁰ Code-switched reiterations are oriented to the recipient’s involvement in the interaction.

¹²¹ Shannon and Weaver 1949.

¹²² Reliability is a matter of literal analysis, historical accuracy is the territory of the historian. Culpepper 1983: 32.

¹²³ Carey 2009: 153-154.

¹²⁴ His codeswitching is a literary device, ‘not because of confusion or inability to separate the two languages, but a conscious desire to juxtapose the two codes to achieve some literary effect, an exercise of self-consciousness’. Lipski 1982: 191.

¹²⁵ Hosanna and amen appear translated in the LXX by σῶσον δὴ and ἀληθῶς or γένοιτο, but Mark leaves them untranslated, which means that they were known and used in their community. The Greek translation of Ps. 22.2 (πρόσχεζ μοι ἴνα) does not match Mark’s.

¹²⁶ The opinions of the Greco-Roman elites are contrary to Judaism. In fact, the Roman elites were the last to embrace Christianity. Johnston 1897: 51.

Mark uses two different Aramaic local names, Gehenna and Golgotha, and then translates them into Greek. The function of this translation codeswitching in relation to placenames is to specify and concretize a place possibly known to some members of the community. Indeed, they have a reference and descriptive value. On the other hand, they give credibility and reliability to the narrative. Both Gehenna and Golgotha, are used rhetorically and give emphasis to the story. The translation of Golgotha as the 'place of the skull' is expressive of the drama that looms in the crucifixion¹²⁷. The words 'into the unquenchable fire' associated with Gehenna¹²⁸ reinforce Jesus' warning. Both have a dramatic effect. The translation 'the preparation day, that is, the day before the Sabbath' has a similar function. It functions as a description commentary and fulfils a metaphorical purpose¹²⁹.

Several Aramaic proper names appear in Mark (Barabbas, Thadeus, Thomas). Their appearance gives reliability to the story, because these names must have been known to the community. An interesting case is the switch of code with Boanerges and Bartimeus. Boanerges was the nickname that Jesus gave to James and John, as it was still remembered by the community many years later. These cases display several functions: they fulfil an addressee specification function and allow Mark, on the one hand to characterize Bartimeus as an Aramaic speaker, and on the other hand John and Andrew as 'strong people' (reflecting a metaphorical use¹³⁰).

Among the significant Aramaic words that appear in Mark are *rabbi* and *rabbouni*, the titles which were used by Jesus' disciples to address him. The title *rabbi* conveys a sense of Jesus' particular greatness. In three of the four instances, Jesus is called *rabbi* in response to a miraculous action on his part¹³¹. Surprisingly, these words are not translated¹³², which suggests that they were already part of the vocabulary of his community. Mark is recalling a usage that goes back to the first disciples of Jesus. He links the Gospel to the chain of transmission and therefore gives reliability to the narrator. Its use functions as an addressee specification, as a title, as a vocative and it fulfils a metaphorical function. The word *rabbi* appears in connection with several miracles of Jesus.

The appearance of the Aramaic word *korban* gives emphasis and surprise to Jesus' words. The functions of this codeswitching are: referential, lexical need and message qualification (in fact, Mark needs to explain it). Its use intensifies and eliminates ambiguity and it has a metaphorical use, due to its connection with Judaism.

The two Aramaic sentences and their translations that follow are very important in the Gospel. With these words Jesus demonstrates his power and authority¹³³. Jesus has used these words to raise a girl from the dead (*talita kum*) and with another word (*efatta*) he cures a deaf mute¹³⁴. These are two imperatives, two orders from Jesus, that save two

¹²⁷ Linguistically no explanation has been found for this correspondence between the Aramaic word and its translation. Collins 2007: 738.

¹²⁸ In fact, its threefold appearance gives cohesion and connection to the Jesus' speech.

¹²⁹ It is called 'metaphorical use' when the purpose of introducing a particular variety into the conversation is to evoke the connotations, the metaphorical 'world' of that variety. Gardner-Chloros 2009: 59.

¹³⁰ The metaphor behinds is thunder as STRONG.

¹³¹ Bartimaeus' reference to Jesus as *rabbouni* is coupled with the address 'son of David' (10.47, 48), suggesting that the term should be thought of as meaning 'sir' or perhaps 'lord', and not 'teacher'. Marcus 2009: 633.

¹³² Neither is the word Christ translated. Not so in John, where the word Messiah appears and *rabbi* and *rabbouni* are translated. Still today it's impressive the study on the word *rabbi* in Hengel 1968: 46-55.

¹³³ Gnilka 1978a: 216. Gnilka analyzes the relationship of Jesus' words with the theme of the command to silence pp. 210. Theißen 1974: 151.

¹³⁴ The two Aramaic expressions are the verbal complement to two non-verbal healings and they are indeed in a closed space. Mussies 1984: 427. For Joel Marcus, preserving Aramaic increases the mystery and

people. Both orders are fulfilled immediately as indicated by the adverb εὐθέως, which reinforces the performance and power of Jesus¹³⁵. These are two metaphorical uses; firstly, sleep as a metaphor of DEATH (rising as a metaphor of awakening, of living) and secondly, opening as a metaphor of the PATH from isolation to relationship, since the deaf mute's mouth and ears were closed, unable to speak or hear.

The sentence '*Talitá kum*, which means: Girl, I tell you, get up', is a case of codeswitching of repetition and translation. It is clear, particularly by the addition of the expression 'I tell you', that it is not a literal translation. This sentence reinforces the power of Jesus' word, his prominence, his authority, his commitment to healing¹³⁶, as well as his personal relationship with the child. This same expression also appears in another healing narrative (2.11-12) and is followed by the same imperative: get up! Similarly, the adverb εὐθύς appears there indicating the immediacy of healing as in this case¹³⁷. On the other hand, in this expression a fundamental NT verb appears: 'Get up'. The verb *kum* in Hebrew and Aramaic has a literal meaning that is to rise, and a metaphorical meaning that is to resurrect. Mark wants this resurrection to be related to that of Jesus¹³⁸. Jesus orders the girl to rise (ἔγειρε), the same word with which it will be said that Jesus has been risen from death (ἠγέρθη 16.6). The girl stood up (ἀνέστη), just as Jesus will rise (ἀναστήσεται), overcoming death (8.31; 9.31; 10.34).

The command of Jesus 'and he said to him: *Effatá*, that means: be opened!' (7.34) is another case of codeswitching of translation and repetition. Mark perfectly translates this divine passive¹³⁹, but his translation brings a new nuance, since the meaning of the verb *διανοίγω* is to 'open completely'¹⁴⁰. Surprisingly, with the words 'Open up' Jesus addresses the man and not his diseased organs¹⁴¹. Therefore, the relationship with Jesus is in the foreground. Also in this case the healing happens instantaneously.

The functions of these two codeswitchings (*Talita kumi* and *Effatá*) are similar. They give emphasis to the narrative given their surprising appearance and they also slow the discourse and attract the reader's attention. Their use reinforces the miracle and recalls Jesus' use of these words.

Another case of intraclause codeswitching is the expression *αββα ὁ πατήρ*. It is an expression known in Christianity (Gal. 4.6 and Rom. 8.15). *Abba*¹⁴² is the word with

gives suspense. Marcus 2000: 363, 372 and 479. On the magic formulas and the command of silence. cf. Theißen 1974: 143-153.

¹³⁵ καὶ εὐθύς ἀνέστη (5.42); καὶ εὐθέως ἠνοίγησαν (7.35). There are problems of textual criticism with the adverb εὐθέως in this second case.

¹³⁶ Focant 2012: 215.

¹³⁷ σοὶ λέγω, ἔγειρε... καὶ ἠγέρθη καὶ εὐθύς (Mk. 2.11-12) = σοὶ λέγω, ἔγειρε (5.41).

¹³⁸ For Aichele in Mark's story it is not known if the girl is asleep or dead. So while the Aramaic sentence is a normal one that could be said to a girl, the Greek translation contains a formula, a recipe for resurrection. This confrontation reproduces the fundamental indeterminacy of Mark's story. Aichele 1996: 70-71.

¹³⁹ *Effatá* is a divine passive, 'be opened!'. It's the transliteration of *ippetah* (assimilated form of *itpetah* *ܐܦܬܗ*). It would be the *hitpe'el* imperative of *ܦܬܗ*. Marcus 2000: 475 and 479.

¹⁴⁰ Mark translates *effata* by *διανοίχθητι*. For Gundry the preposition *δια* creates a perfective sense: 'become completely open', it would be in this case a translation that clarifies and reinforces. Gundry 1993: 384.

¹⁴¹ Gnlika 1978a: 295-299. Lincicum's thesis that Jesus' command would be referred to God does not carry much weight. Lincicum 2015.

¹⁴² About *abba*, cf. Chilton 2009. Zimmermann 2007. Fitzmyer 1993. Jeremias 1966. Surprisingly, the Peshitta translates *ܐܒܘܐܒܘܐ* *abba, abbi*, (father, my father) and not *ܐܒܒܐܢܐ*, *ܐܒܒܐܢܐ* which would be the vocative (since the first person in the plural is the vocative in Syriac), as it appears in the Lord's Prayer in Mt. 6.9. Here the Peshitta follows the Greek. According to Van Iersel, 'the Aramaic 'abbā is somewhat clumsily translated into Greek as the nominative ὁ πατήρ, instead of the obvious vocative πάτερ. The Roman Christians know the word *abba* from Rom. 8.15, 42 which also has *αββα ὁ πατήρ*, and not the vocative. The vocative *πάτερ* occurs in Matthew four times, in Luke eleven times, and in John eight

which Jesus addressed God in his prayer and reflects a surprising use of it, as also the word *amen*. These are uses unknown in their time, or at least surprising. These words of Jesus were fixed in the memory of his disciples¹⁴³. This switch of code give emphasis, and solemnity to this important moment in Jesus' life. It functions as vocative and addressee specification and evokes a metaphorical use. Its use is also a reminder of Jesus (and therefore highlights the narrator's reliability) and a possible liturgical practice (Gal. 4.6).

In Hebrew and Aramaic the word *amen* (in Hebrew אמן, from the root 'mn, which means to be firm, credible) is a response that expresses approval, confirmation and appropriation of the words by a third party, while in the Gospels it introduces a discourse of Jesus and endows it with authority¹⁴⁴. On the other hand, the Greek word ἀμήν only appears 6 times in the LXX. Typically, the LXX translates the word אמן by γένοιτο¹⁴⁵.

The social functions of the intraclause case of codeswitching 'ἀμήν λέγω ὑμῖν' in Mark are the following. 1) The expression ἀμήν λέγω ὑμῖν is a discourse marker and an interjection. 2) It is used to draw someone's attention. The object of attention of this expression is the following saying and it is always hosted in a unit of discourse. It has a deictic function, which could be regarded as its semantic core. Amen is primarily a lexical marker of mirativity, the linguistic marking for indicating that the information conveyed is new or unexpected to the speaker¹⁴⁶. 3) It also introduces a quotation, a following important message. For Fowler: the 'truly (*amen*), I say to you' saying can be used to communicate either an interpretation, a judgment, or a generalization to the reader. By using *amen* these sayings function as a striking form of solemn asseveration¹⁴⁷. 4) It provokes emphasis and solemnity to his words. Therefore, its appearance in Mark reinforces the content of them. 5) Its huge appearance gives cohesion and connection to the Jesus' sayings. 6) The narrative and the discourse slow down, preparing the reader for something important. 7) The reader's attention is drawn with a marked element, by four reasons. a) The presence of an Aramaic word. b) Amen would be expected at the end of the sentence, not at the beginning. c) It appears as a case of codeswitching with Aramaic. d) It's embedded in a fixed expression. 8) Its use remembers Jesus. It joins the succession of witnesses. This word connects the reader directly with the living memory of Jesus. Therefore, it enhances trustworthiness to the words of Jesus delivered in his Gospel. 9) This formula evokes a prophetic utilization, reinforcing the status of Jesus as a prophet¹⁴⁸, therefore it also manifests a metaphorical background. 10) The receiver community confirms its identity and belonging with Jesus and Christianity. Through this expression the author converges with his audience who know the expression. 11) The author is presented as a credible transmitter and interpreter (Trustworthiness).

Mark uses the Aramaic word *hosanna* but does not translate it¹⁴⁹, since it is certain that in Jesus' time, as well as in his community, it was a known expression of exclamation

times; the alternative ὁ πατήρ does not occur in the Gospels except in Mt. 11.26 par. Lk. 10.2 (πάτερ), and in the three places connected to one another through abba: Mk 14.36; Rom. 8.15; Gal. 4.6'. Van Iersel 1998: 434. For the nominative with the article as an alternative for the vocative see Blass, Debrunner and Funk 1962: 81–82, §147.

¹⁴³ About memory and Christology cf. Du Toit 2015.

¹⁴⁴ Zumstein 2014. Lee 2012: 349-360. Amen is used by Jesus at the beginning of the sentences and not at the end as it appears in the OT.

¹⁴⁵ In Jer. 28.6 (Jer. 35.6 LXX) amen is translated by ἀληθῶς, a use that also appears in Luke when he translates amen into Greek.

¹⁴⁶ DeLancey 2001: 369-370.

¹⁴⁷ Fowler 1991: 128 and 77. Significantly, 'amen' and 'whoever' statements are frequently intertwined.

¹⁴⁸ According to Joachim Jeremias the only parallel would be the formula 'thus says the Lord'. Jeremias 1971: 36.

¹⁴⁹ Brown 1994: 1247. The translation in the LXX is σῶσον δὴ and Mark does not rely on it.

or praise, given its liturgical use¹⁵⁰ (Jn. 12.13, Did. 10.6). The word refers to Ps. 118.25 and appears linked to the entrance of Jesus into Jerusalem¹⁵¹, where Jesus is praised as one who comes in the name of the Lord¹⁵². That is to say, its use recalls a very significant scene in the life of Jesus and refers to the prayer of the Jewish people. Jesus is praised with an expression that refers to the Kingdom of God and to God himself. This word fulfills several functions. Firstly, it acts as a discourse marker and an interjection, giving solemnity to his followers' words. These two recurrences give cohesion and connection to this acclamation. Secondly, it refers the reader to a Psalm (quoting function). The entrance of Jesus is linked to the Psalm that praised the entrance of God into the Temple. Thirdly, this word recalls a significant historical moment in the life of Jesus that should have been registered in the memory of the witnesses. Fourthly, this exclamation surprises the reader and reminds them of the liturgical use of it in the community, a use that does not need translation or presentation. Fifthly, it reinforces the reliability of the narrator.

Turning to the last words of Jesus on the cross (Mk 15.34), there are a number of observations to be made. Firstly, it is a case of intrasentential codeswitching of repetition and translation. Secondly, Mark's quotation in Aramaic and his translation (which is not that of the LXX) enhance the importance of the narrator. Thirdly, in the context of the story, it has been pointed out that Mark's translation of the Aramaic expression allows only the reader to understand correctly the death of Jesus, because his cry was misinterpreted by the characters in the story: the cry to God (Eloi) is misunderstood as a cry to Elijah (Elias). Therefore, no character in the story understood Jesus' dying words. 'In a profound sense, the only genuine witness to the crucifixion in Mark is the reader¹⁵³'. Fourthly, the last words of Jesus are a quotation from a psalm (Ps. 22.1) originally written in Hebrew, yet he expresses them in Aramaic and not in Hebrew¹⁵⁴. This prayer (where Jesus addresses God with the Aramaic word Eloi) forms an inclusion with the beginning of the story of the Passion¹⁵⁵, where in another prayer Jesus addresses God as 'Abba, Father'. In this sense the social function of the Aramaic expression 'Eloi, Eloi, lama sabtani' is also very important¹⁵⁶. Jesus does not pray the Psalms in the official language of the Temple and the synagogue, but in the language of the common people. In Qumran the Psalms and liturgical texts were prayed in Hebrew and not in Aramaic¹⁵⁷. It is consistent with the attitude of Jesus towards the Temple and the elite¹⁵⁸ and with his desire to bring the message of God in a language intelligible to the simple people (as for example in his parables). Therefore, its functions include emphasis and surprise to the reader. Its appearance slows the discourse, and generates an irony and a misunderstanding to the characters. This use gives credibility and reliability to the narrator, reinforcing the author's role as interpreter of the message of Jesus and guarantor of its transmission.

¹⁵⁰ Indeed, *hosanna* could be related to Jesus' name. Gundry 1993: 630.

¹⁵¹ This root does not appear in the Targum and is translated by the Aramaic root פָּרַח.

¹⁵² According to Gnilka it could be an exhortation to the angels to join in the praise. Gnilka 1978b: 119-120.

¹⁵³ Fowler 1991: 109.

¹⁵⁴ The codex Bezae quotes them in Mishnaic Hebrew.

¹⁵⁵ Brown 1994: 1240.

¹⁵⁶ According to Fowler those words are misunderstood by everyone in the Gospel as the reference to Elijah demonstrates. Only the reader understands them well and only he becomes a witness. Fowler 1991: 109. Carey 2009: 152-155. Theobald 2010. Trudinger 1974. Buckler 1938. Danker 1970. Lee 2012: 320-325.

¹⁵⁷ Flint 1997. Surely the Aramaic texts of Qumran are not sectarian but they were carried there. Joosten 2010a: 364.

¹⁵⁸ About the temple in Mark cf. Gray 2008.

5.4 *The function of the Hebrew theophoric names*

An aspect that is not very well-known is the political-religious function of the use of theophoric and Hebrew names that appear in Mark¹⁵⁹. They are names that refer to God and that in Hebrew have a deep meaning¹⁶⁰. Likewise, these names recall and evoke historical figures from Israel's past that have deep national, religious and political connotations, as well as events that recall hope. It must be remembered that the name 'Jesus'¹⁶¹ is the same as 'Joshua' in Hebrew, and is transliterated in the same way in Greek: Ἰησοῦς. The name Jesus, ('Yahweh saves' according to Mt. 1.21) is a declaration of principles. Joshua was the successor of Moses, who gathered the tribes, crossed the Jordan and conquered the promised land. This name Joshua (= Jesus), was the sixth most popular name of his time in Palestine¹⁶², (after Simon, Joseph, Lazarus, Judah and John). Six of the most popular names at this time were those of the Hasmonean family, those of Mattathias and their five children¹⁶³. They were patriotic names. These names indicate the social and religious – political desire at the time of Jesus. The name Jesus recalled surely the liberation and reconquest of the earth to the Romans¹⁶⁴, as did those of Elijah, John, Jacob (James), Judah, Levi, Abiathar, Abraham, Isaac, Joseph, Moses, David; names that refer to Yahweh or the history of Israel.

The function performed by these names is fourfold. In the first place, they refer to the real characters of the story that underlie Mark's story, which reinforces its historicity¹⁶⁵. Secondly, these names evoke the main characters in the history of Israel, linking their story with Jewish history and its worldview. Thirdly, these names recall the deep belief of Israel: 'only Yahweh is God'. Fourthly, these characters reinforce the identity of the community by sympathizing with Judaism and the history of God and the Jewish people.

5.5 *The function of the Latin language in Mark*

Before discussing the function of Latin in Mark it must be pointed out that there was a long relationship of language contact between Latin and Greek, although Greek exerted more influence on Latin than vice versa¹⁶⁶. Even so, it is a complex relationship with different manifestations depending on the specific community being considered¹⁶⁷. Therefore, Latinisms in the Greek language are not rare¹⁶⁸, they are even common in Greek papyri¹⁶⁹. As pointed out earlier, the frequency with which they appear in Mark is very high, for a text of the first century.

The use of Latin is not accidental in Mark, as he tries through loanwords to find the right term to be understood by his community. They are loanwords and expressions that are typical of a multilingual author, who finds a better synonym in a word from another

¹⁵⁹ Mussies 1984: 416-422.

¹⁶⁰ Cf. n. 49, where the translations of these Hebrew theophoric names are detailed.

¹⁶¹ Yehosua, Joshua, theophoric name whose first element is Yahu = Yahweh and the second the imperative of the verb 'sw help. The true meaning should be: Lord save me! After this Yehosua was abbreviated to Yoshua and later to Yeshua. Fitzmyer 2006: 117.

¹⁶² Ilan, Ziem and Hünefeld 2002: 91, 126, 141, 148. Helen 1981.

¹⁶³ Simon was the most popular one. Ilan, Ziem and Hünefeld 2002: 56.

¹⁶⁴ Bauckham 2006: 76.

¹⁶⁵ In 1 Cor. 15 and Gal. 1-2 all these characters appear.

¹⁶⁶ Binder 2000.

¹⁶⁷ 'There was not a uniform diglossic relationship between Greek and Latin under the Roman Empire'. Adams 2003: 754.

¹⁶⁸ The word legio, λεγεών that appears in Mark is found as such in the inscriptions of Palmyra as LGYWN.

¹⁶⁹ Dickey 2012. García Domingo 1978.

language¹⁷⁰. These words in Latin were commonly used¹⁷¹ and several of these Latinisms appear even in Jesus' words in direct speech (2.9: 4.21; 12.15,16). However, in Mark the Latin words, unlike the Aramaic ones, do not have to be explained, they merely provide the right word and concept to the reader (12.42 and 15.16).

Only the word legion develops a special literary function in the narrative, giving emphasis and attracting the reader's attention. The ironic and dramatic effect of the term is underlined given its connection with the unclean spirit and the pigs. This loanword also plays a metaphorical use characterizing the unclean spirit as a multitude (LEGION as multitude) and also as POWERFUL as the legions of Rome.

The striking fact is not the presence of so many Latin loanwords but the cases of codeswitching and translation (12.14 and 15.16) in which Mark goes from the Greek to the Latin translation (see the formula ὃ ἐστίν, to explain Greek terms). They are two commentaries of the narrator. Few authors would have chosen a Latin loanword (quadran and praetorium) to explain a Greek term (λεπτός and ἀλῆς) if they did not live in a context where that language was widely spoken. This fact could be a deciding factor in order to place the Gospel of Mark in Rome.

The price that Mark has to pay for the inclusion of Latin loanwords is that they are a further contributory element to the low style of his Greek narrative¹⁷², something that would not, however, have mattered to its author.

The presence of Latin (words that in Mark's case concern the civil and military and not the familiar or religious domains) and its reference to the Empire¹⁷³ consciously or unconsciously recalls the context of power, and the persecuted community in which Christianity is found (the expulsion of the Jews from Rome under Claudius, the persecution of Nero¹⁷⁴, the deaths of Peter and Paul, etc.). These Latin loanwords recall also that Jesus was killed on the cross,¹⁷⁵ a Roman torture. Surprisingly, in Mark there is no explicit rejection of Rome, although there is maybe a sustained criticism. In fact, Rome is neutrally presented in some passages, whereas several of the Latin loanwords (e.g. *flagellar*, *census*¹⁷⁶, *caesar*, *legion*¹⁷⁷, *centurio*, *denarius*¹⁷⁸, *speculator*) would have a pejorative connotation. Therefore, their function and their associative capacity is very different from the Aramaic, provoking rather negative connotations.

¹⁷⁰ For Joel Marcus those Greek words are nuanced by more precise Latin words. Marcus 2000: 31. Mark tries to accommodate to his readers when he uses Latin. 'Communication Accommodation Theory' (Giles and Ogay 2007) affirms that speakers sometimes try to accommodate to the expectations that others have of them. Accommodation allows to explain how individuals and groups may be seen to relate to each other.

¹⁷¹ For Martin Hengel the Latinisms are evidence of the provenance of Mark from Rome. Hengel also recalls that John Markus had a Latin cognomen. Hengel 1984: 44. Also for Incigneri 2003: 101. Not so for Cadbury and Atchmeier who consider those words very used throughout the empire. Cadbury 1958: 88-89. Achtemeier 2004: 114-115. The words *Καίσαρος*, *κεντυρίων*, *κησος*, *μοδιον*, *ξεστης*, *πραιτωριον*, *λεγιων*, *σπεκουλατωρ*, appear in the Greek papyri found in Egypt. It would be necessary to date their appearance. Cf. Daris 1971. Cervenka-Ehrenstrasser and Diethart 1996.

¹⁷² It contrasts with the use of codeswitching in Cicero, which appears in some of his works. Swain 2002.

¹⁷³ Leander 2013.

¹⁷⁴ Cf. Hurtado 2016: 39-40 where he exposes the opinions of Tacitus and Suetonius about Christianity as an identifiable group in Rome in the year 60 when the persecution against them was declared.

¹⁷⁵ Cook 2014.

¹⁷⁶ *Census* means tax. The political and religious connotations of the word are clear to Judaism, as evidenced by the revolt of Judah the Galilean (Act. 5.17).

¹⁷⁷ A demoniac identifies his demons with the legions. A very pejorative identification.

¹⁷⁸ It is enough to remember the controversy and the crisis by the effigies with Judaism. Josephus, *B.J.* 2.169-174.

6 Conclusion

Having analyzed the different functions of loanwords and codeswitching between Greek, Aramaic, Hebrew and Latin in Mark, we can conclude the following:

1. The application of sociolinguistic tools to the Gospel of Mark and especially to his multilingualism has proved fruitful in providing significant information about the author, the text and the receiving community.

2. Lexical borrowing and codeswitching are two deliberate strategies used by Mark through which he fulfills certain social and literary functions, which reinforce his leadership as interpreter of the Jesus tradition.

3. The switches of code from Greek to Aramaic allow Mark to reinforce the reliability of his narrative and its historical character and permit him to link his story with Jesus and his disciples, with the beginning of the Christian community and with the Jewish community. In this regard, the Hebrew names that appear in his Gospel recall the Hebrew Bible and several historical places and persons which are important for the Christian community. Nevertheless, the changes to Latin have an explanatory function and work differently to those changes in Aramaic, the principal function of which is to emphasise Jesus' words. The Aramaic words evoke Jesus and his disciples, whereas the Latin words tend to fill several linguistics gaps that could recall the status of dominion of the Empire, an Empire that killed Jesus.

4. This linguistic use of Aramaic, Hebrew and Latin are not neutral. It distances Mark from the Greco-Roman elites because these 'barbarisms' and his simple style are very far from the literary works that aim to imitate the classical Attic style.

5. Lastly, it has been shown that there are linguistic characteristics that link Mark's Gospel with the LXX and Judaism, as indicated by its anonymity, its prologue and the numerous references and citations of the LXX. Mark adopts the dialect variety of the LXX as well as its worldview and narrative world. His idiolect is therefore the result of conscious choices and its main function is to reinforce the identity of its community¹⁷⁹, generating cohesion and belonging with Jesus and Christianity. If the community listens and uses the same words that Jesus and his disciples used, its identity as Jesus' followers is once more confirmed. This language strategy unites the community with the original witnesses and reinforces its belonging to the Christian movement.

¹⁷⁹ 'Language is not only a means of communicating but also a very important symbol of group identification and peer-group solidarity. Individual identity and social identity are mediated by language, with linguistic features the link that binds both together'. Tabouret-Keller 1997: 317.

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